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WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN NIGERIA BANKING INDUSTRY

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking industry. The descriptive survey research designs the cross-sectional strategy to obtain data from the respondents. The population consists of bank employees in Rivers State, Nigeria. A sample size of 310 bank employees was determined using purposive sampling and Taro Yamen's formula. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to participants, with a high response rate of 90.7%, resulting in 281 usable responses. Analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings indicate a significant positive correlation between role engagement and all dimensions of organizational commitment, as well as between role conflict and organizational commitment. These results underscore the importance of fostering work-life balance initiatives to enhance organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking sector. Recommendations include implementing flexible work arrangements, supporting employee well-being, and providing training opportunities to improve work-life balance skills.

Keywords

Role Conflict. Role Engagement. Affective Commitment. Continuance Commitment.

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INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of the Nigerian banking industry, the significance of work-life balance has gained traction and interest of industry experts and scholars alike (Adegbite, 2019). People stand as the invaluable assets of any organization, serving as the driving force behind its competitive edge (Rashmi &Kataria, 2022). However, this edge is only attainable when employees find satisfaction in their roles. Employee satisfaction lays the foundation for business success, reflected in reduced absenteeism rates, heightened productivity, and enhanced service quality. Consequently, fostering employee engagement becomes imperative, leading to increased retention rates and overall organizational prosperity (Markos& Sridevi, 2010; Rashmi &Kataria, 2022).

To maintain employee quality and commitment essential for meeting organizational targets, many organizations are increasingly adopting work-life balance programs (Lazar, *et. al.*, 2010). Work-life balance encompasses a harmonious equilibrium between work responsibilities and personal life; ensuring employees have adequate time, manage work pressures, and nurture personal pursuits. At its core, this program embodies principles of moral intelligence and motivation, fostering self-management, responsibility, and overall well-being (Gautam & Jain, 2018). The aim is to enhance employees' quality of life, fostering physical and mental well-being, and cultivating a sense of fulfilment beyond the confines of work (Lazar, *et. al.*, 2010; Markos& Sridevi, 2010; Sheppard, 2016).

Ensuring a healthy work-life balance is imperative for sustaining organizational commitment, particularly in the dynamic landscape of the Nigerian banking industry (Ekpechi&Igwe, 2023). Several scholarly works shed light on this relationship, elucidating its significance and implications. Chandel, *et. al.* (2023), undertakes a comprehensive analysis of how work-life balance influences various dimensions of organizational commitment within the banking sector. Similarly, Bourke, *et. al.*(2021) offers a structured overview of existing literature, providing insights into the multifaceted nature of work-life balance and its intricate implication and possible connection with organizational commitment. Furthermore, Wood, *et. al.* (2020) explores the interplay between work engagement and work-life balance, emphasizing the pivotal role of achieving equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal well-being in fostering sustained commitment among bank employees.

With consideration to the dynamic nature of the Nigerian banking industry, where intense work demands often intersect with cultural and familial obligations, the significance of work-

life balance cannot be overstated. Malik and Noreen (2015) underscores the impact of factors such as work stress, job control, and organizational support on employee well-being, thereby influencing their commitment to the organization. These scholarly works underscore the intricate relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment.

The implementation of work-life balance initiatives is anticipated to transcend mere professional obligations, enabling employees to lead fulfilling lives encompassing family and social spheres. By fostering balance and happiness, these programs hold the potential to elevate organizational commitment and performance within the Nigerian banking sector (Ekpechi & Igwe, 2023; Mmakwe & Ukoha, 2018). In light of these considerations, this research study aims to delve into the intricate relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment within the Nigerian banking industry. Through empirical investigation and analysis, this study seeks to provide insights that can inform organizational policies and practices, fostering a conducive work environment that nurtures both employee well-being and organizational success.

Objectives

The objective of this study was to investigate the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment specifically within the context of the Nigerian banking industry.

The study specifically aims to:

- i) Investigate the relationship between role engagement and affective commitment.
- ii) Examine the relationship between role engagement and continuance commitment
- iii) Examine the relationship between role engagement and normative commitment
- iv) Investigate the relationship between role conflict and affective commitment
- v) Investigate the relationship between role conflict and continuance commitment
- vi) Examine the relationship between role conflict and normative commitment

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Role Theory

Role theory is a fundamental concept in sociology and social psychology that delves into the intricate dynamics of social behaviour through the lens of socially defined categories known as roles (Biddle, 1986; Michalec & Hafferty, 2015). These roles encompass a set of rights, duties, expectations, norms, and behaviours that individuals are expected to fulfil within

society. This theory suggests that individuals play multiple roles in their personal and professional lives, and the ability to balance these roles is very crucial (Sirgy & Lee, 2023).

The theoretical foundations of role theory trace back to the pioneering works of sociologists and psychologists, one prominent among being Mead (1934). Mead's concepts of the mind and the self laid the groundwork for role theory, highlighting the interplay between individual identity and social interaction (Ritzer, 2007). Rooted in the observation of predictable human behaviour, the role theory emphasizes the context-specific nature of individual actions, influenced by social position and other contextual factors (Eagly & Wood, 2012).

Despite its significance in understanding social dynamics, role theory has faced criticism. It has been accused of reinforcing prejudices, overlooking power dynamics, and inadequately explaining individual agency in negotiating roles (Biddle, 1986). Nonetheless, role theory remains a pivotal framework for analyzing social behaviour and the dynamics of the interaction between job roles and organizational commitment. Role Theory provides a framework for understanding how the balance (or imbalance) between professional and personal roles can impact organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking industry. It suggests that initiatives to improve work-life balance can lead to increased organizational commitment (Sirgy & Lee, 2018; Sirgy & Lee, 2023).

Spillover Theory

Spillover theory, introduced by Staines in 1980, offers valuable insights into the interconnectedness of various life domains and the consequences of balancing multiple roles. At its core, spillover theory posits that emotions, attitudes, behaviours, and experiences from one domain, such as work, can extend into other areas of life, such as the family domain (Rincy & Panchanatham, 2014; Zimmerman & Hammer, 2010). The essence of spillover theory lies in understanding how experiences in one domain, whether positive or negative, influence and spill over into other domains. For instance, if an individual experiences dissatisfaction or stress at work, they may carry these negative emotions home, affecting their personal life and relationships (Judge & Ilies, 2004; Khalid, 2023).

Guest (2002) further elaborates on spillover theory, highlighting the conditions under which spillover between work and family domains occurs. This spillover can be either positive or negative, depending on the structure of work-family interactions. When work-family interactions are rigid and inflexible in terms of time and space, negative spillover occurs,

leading to conflicts and stress. Conversely, when individuals have flexibility to integrate and overlap work and family responsibilities, positive spillover occur, contributing to a healthy work-life balance (Khateeb, 2021; Mmakwe&Ukoha, 2018).

The Spillover Theory provides a framework for understanding how the interplay between work and personal life can impact work-life balance and, consequently, organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking industry. It suggests that initiatives to manage this spillover can lead to improved work-life balance and increased organizational commitment (Khateeb, 2021).

Concept of Work-Life Balance (WLB)

The concept of work-life balance holds significant relevance within the Nigerian banking industry, where employees often grapple with the demands of their professional roles alongside personal responsibilities (Ojo, 2016). Work-life balance encompasses the equilibrium between professional responsibilities and personal well-being, acknowledging the bidirectional interaction between work and personal life domains (Cvenkel, 2020).

Work-life balance is a concept that refers to an individual's ability to maintain a healthy equilibrium between their professional responsibilities and personal life. It involves managing one's time, resources, and energy across various roles in both work and non-work domains (Sirgy& Lee, 2018). The idea of work-life balance programs emerged in response to the challenges of work-life conflict faced by employees arising when the demands of an employee's job clash with their personal life, such as their roles as a spouse, parent, or their involvement in religious or leisure activities (Mmakwe&Ukoha, 2018). Within the context of the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment two variables can be identified to play significant roles; they are role engagement and role conflict (Sirgy& Lee, 2018).

Role Engagement

Role engagement refers to the extent to which individuals actively participate and invest themselves in their professional roles within the organization (Sirgy& Lee, 2018). Role engagement encompasses the active and enthusiastic participation in multiple roles across both professional and personal domains. It signifies a state of being fully immersed and invested in fulfilling responsibilities and achieving goals in various facets of life, including work and non-work spheres. This concept can be elucidated from several perspectives, each

highlighting different aspects of engagement and its alignment with individuals' life goals and aspirations (Sirgy& Lee, 2018; Sirgy& Lee, 2023; Thilagavathy& Geetha, 2021).

Firstly, role engagement entails experiencing equal levels of satisfaction and involvement in both work-related and non-work-related activities. Moreover, role engagement is characterized by the alignment of work and non-work roles with individuals' life goals and aspirations. This perspective emphasizes the importance of pursuing roles and responsibilities that resonate with one's values, beliefs, and long-term objectives, fostering a sense of purpose and meaning in both domains (Sirgy& Lee, 2023).

Successful accomplishment of goals in both work and non-work domains is another dimension of role engagement. Individuals who are fully engaged in their roles demonstrate competence and efficacy in achieving their objectives, whether they pertain to career advancement, personal growth, or fulfilling familial and social responsibilities (Sirgy& Lee, 2023). In essence, role engagement encompasses a multifaceted approach to active participation and fulfilment in both work and non-work domains, characterized by equal satisfaction, alignment with life goals, successful goal accomplishment, full immersion, and minimal conflict between roles. Embracing role engagement enables individuals to lead balanced, purposeful, and rewarding lives, contributing to their overall well-being and success (Thilagavathy& Geetha, 2021).

In the Nigerian banking industry, employees who experience a positive work-life balance are more likely to exhibit higher levels of role engagement. When individuals feel supported in managing their work and personal responsibilities, they are better equipped to immerse themselves in their professional roles, contributing actively to the organizational objectives. Moreover, a conducive work-life balance allows employees to derive satisfaction and fulfilment from their work, further enhancing their commitment to the organization (Mmakwe&Ukoha, 2018; Sirgy& Lee, 2018).

Role Conflict

The attainment of work-life balance can be hindered by role conflict, a phenomenon where the demands and expectations of different roles intersect, leading to tension and stress (Robertson, *et. al.*, 2019). Role conflict can manifest in various forms, including time conflicts, strain from conflicting responsibilities, and difficulties in balancing work and family commitments. When employees experience high levels of role conflict, it can

negatively impact their engagement and commitment to their organizational roles, leading to decreased productivity and morale (Lenaghan& Sengupta, 2007).

Role conflict pertains to the challenges and tensions arising from the intersection of social roles in both work and non-work domains. It involves navigating the strains and conflicts that emerge as individuals juggle the demands and expectations associated with their professional and personal responsibilities (Geurts&Demerouti, 2003; Sirgy& Lee, 2018).At its core, role conflict encompasses the struggle to reconcile the obligations and requirements of different roles, whether they pertain to work-related duties or non-work-related commitments. This conflict can manifest in various forms, including time conflicts, where the demands of one role encroach upon the time allocated for another, and strain conflicts, where the stress and pressure from one domain spill over into the other (Sirgy& Lee, 2018).

Managing role conflict requires individuals to adopt strategies to mitigate the tensions and challenges that arise from balancing multiple roles. This may involve setting boundaries between work and personal life, prioritizing tasks and responsibilities, and seeking support from colleagues, friends, or family members. Additionally, fostering open communication and collaboration with employers and stakeholders can help individuals negotiate flexible arrangements and accommodations to alleviate the impact of role conflict (Lenaghan& Sengupta, 2007; Sirgy& Lee, 2023).

By effectively managing role conflict, individuals can strive to achieve a more harmonious and balanced integration of their work and personal life domains. This entails recognizing and addressing the sources of conflict, implementing proactive measures to mitigate its effects, and cultivating resilience and adaptability in navigating the complexities of multiple roles (Cvenkel, 2020; Lenaghan& Sengupta, 2007). In essence, role conflict represents the tension and strain that arises from balancing social roles in work and non-work life. By adopting proactive strategies and seeking support, individuals can minimize the impact of role conflict and strive for a more harmonious integration of their professional and personal responsibilities (Ojo, 2016).

Concept of Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment is a fundamental concept in organizational behaviour and industrial psychology, reflecting the degree of emotional attachment and dedication that employees feel towards their organization (Meyer, *et. al.*, 2004).It is a measure of the extent

to which an employee identifies with their organization and is committed to its goals (Bhat, 2018). Understanding organizational commitment is crucial for fostering a positive work environment, enhancing productivity, and achieving organizational goals (Sharma & Bhati, 2017).

Al-Jabari and Ghazzawi (2019) explain organizational commitment with particular attention to the foundational research into the factors and dimensions that affect employee retention. Mueller, *et.al.* (2020) differentiates attitudinal approaches, conceptualizing commitment as an emotional attachment to the organization, and behavioural approaches, focusing on the behavioural intention to remain in the organization. Similarly, Klein and Park (2015) discusses the evolution of the construct of organizational commitment, overviews the outcomes and antecedents of commitment, contrasts commitment to other related constructs, and outlines current issues in the study of commitment requiring attention in future research.

High levels of organizational commitment have significant implications for both individuals and organizations (Sharma & Bhati, 2017). Employees who are emotionally invested in their work are more likely to demonstrate consistent performance, foster constructive relationships, and contribute positively to the organizational culture (Klein & Park, 2015). Moreover, organizational commitment predicts outcomes such as job satisfaction, turnover rates, and organizational citizenship behaviour, highlighting its critical role in shaping workplace dynamics and organizational success (Bhat, 2018; Sharma & Bhati, 2017). Organizational commitment encompasses various dimensions that influence individuals' decision to remain with their current employer and their level of engagement with their work (Al-Hawary, *et. al.*, 2023).

Dimensions of the Model of Commitment

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment represents the emotional attachment and identification that employees feel towards their organization. It signifies a deep-rooted desire to remain a part of the organization due to a strong alignment with its goals and values. Employees who exhibit high levels of affective commitment are motivated by intrinsic factors and derive satisfaction from their work. This dimension emphasizes the positive emotional bond between individuals and their organization, driving them to contribute actively to its success.

Continuance Commitment

Continuance commitment reflects the perceived costs and benefits associated with staying or leaving the organization. It involves a rational assessment of the investments made in the organization, such as economic and social ties, and the potential losses incurred by seeking alternative employment. Employees with high continuance commitment may remain with the organization out of necessity rather than genuine desire, weighing the practical implications of leaving against the advantages of staying. This dimension highlights the pragmatic considerations that influence employees' commitment to their organization.

Normative Commitment

Normative commitment is rooted in a sense of obligation and duty towards the organization. It stems from internalized norms and values, as well as external factors such as organizational culture and socialization processes. Employees with high normative commitment feel a moral obligation to remain loyal to their organization, often driven by feelings of indebtedness for investments made in their development. This dimension underscores the importance of ethical considerations and social norms in shaping employees' commitment to their organization.

Empirical Review

Malone and Issa (2013) focused on job satisfaction, work-life balance, and organizational commitment among women in the U.S. construction industry. They found that factors such as good working relationships, respect from superiors, job-fit, and opportunities for advancement significantly influenced organizational commitment. This study provides insights into the importance of work-life balance in enhancing commitment to the organization. Similarly, Oyewobiet *al* (2022) investigated the impact of work-life policies (WLPs) on organizational commitment among female construction professionals in Nigeria. They found that work-life balance partially mediated the relationship between WLPs and organizational commitment. This study highlights the role of work-life policies in promoting commitment and emphasizes the relevance of work-life balance initiatives in the Nigerian context.

Caleb *et al.* (2020) explored the predictors of organizational commitment among bankers in Nigeria, focusing on work-life balance and self-efficacy. While work-life balance did not directly influence organizational commitment, self-efficacy significantly predicted

commitment. However, the joint influence of work-life balance and self-efficacy was significant. This study suggests that while work-life balance is important, other factors such as self-efficacy also play a crucial role in determining commitment. Mordiet *al.* (2013) investigated the effect of time usage policies on work-life conflict and the impact of leave programs on employees' attitudes in Nigerian banks. Although the study did not directly examine the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment, it provides insights into the work-life challenges faced by employees in the Nigerian banking sector. This study underscores the importance of addressing work-life balance issues to improve job-related attitudes. Scrima, *et. al.* (2014) investigated the mediating role of work engagement in the relationship between job involvement and affective commitment. While this study did not directly focus on work-life balance, it highlights the importance of employee engagement in fostering commitment to the organization. Work engagement can be influenced by factors such as job involvement, which indirectly relate to work-life balance.

These studies collectively contribute to understanding the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment, albeit from different perspectives. While some studies directly examine this relationship, others focus on related factors such as job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and work engagement. These findings suggest that work-life balance initiatives, such as WLPs and flexible work arrangements, can positively influence organizational commitment, among industries professionals like banking. The current study on work-life balance and organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking industry builds upon these findings by providing empirical evidence specific to the Nigerian context. By incorporating insights from previous research, the current study strengthens the understanding of how work-life balance initiatives can drive organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking sector.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study is concerned with investigating the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment in the Nigerian banking industry. The descriptive survey research design adopted the cross-sectional design strategy of investigation was used in collecting and analysing the study data.

Population for the Study

The population of this study included bank employees randomly selected commercial banks in Rivers States. The population size of this study was determined by adopting the population defined in the study by Madeleine, et al. (2022). The study population was identified as all the employees of commercial banks in Nigeria, specifically focusing on 19 selected banks in Rivers State with a total of 1,382 employees.

Sample Procedure/Sample Size Determination

The researcher adopted purposive sampling of the non-probability sampling method, because with this method all items are selected on the bases of researchers' convenience (Baridam, 2010). The sample size of the study was statistically determined using the Taro Yamen's formula (Baridam,2001) at 95% confidence interval. A sample size of 310 bank employees was drawn.

Data Collection Method

The adopted source of data in this study was the primary data source. The primary source of data was obtained through the distribution of questionnaire. The researcher adopted the questionnaire method as a primary source for data collection because the questionnaire can be given to many participants at the same time. Questionnaire is encompassing as almost every problem in administrative sciences can be tackled with this method of data collection (Baridam 2001).

The questionnaire was designed after an extensive literature review. The questionnaire was divided into two parts (Part 1 & 2). Part 1 contains the demographic information of respondent, while Part 2 was further divided into two sections and consists of questions relating to the subject matter of inquiry. The questionnaire was structured along the Likert 5 – point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SA) with a corresponding value of 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1.

Operational Measures

For the independent variable of work-life balance, the dimensions of role engagement and role conflict are examined. Role engagement is measured through assessing equal engagement and satisfaction in work and non-work domains, alignment of roles with life goals, successful goal accomplishment, full engagement in multiple life domains, and

minimal role conflict. Role conflict is operationalized by evaluating time conflicts, strain conflicts, and behavioural conflicts between work and non-work roles. On the other hand, the dependent variable of organizational commitment is assessed through dimensions including affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment. Affective commitment is measured by evaluating emotional attachment and desire to continue employment, while continuance commitment is assessed by examining perceived costs associated with leaving the organization. Normative commitment is operationalized through gauging feelings of obligation and societal influences on commitment decisions.

Validity and Reliability

Content and Face validity was utilized in the study to establish the construct validity of the survey tool. The validation of the survey tools was accomplished through a peer review process involving academics in the field. Interrater reliability testing was implemented to ascertain the consistency of the research tool across different respondents. This was confirmed by applying the Cronbach alpha test to the instrument. The reliability of the variables in the questionnaires was tested using SPSS version 25.0. The reliability data is presented below.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics using Cronbach's alpha.

Constructs	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
Role Engagement:	3	0.702
Role Conflict:	3	0.816
Affective Commitment:	3	0.820
Continuance Commitment:	3	0.747
Normative Commitment:	3	0.829
Overall variable	18	0.838

Method of Data Analysis

The researcher employed tables and frequencies to analyze the demographic distribution of the study sample. Mean and standard deviation was used to analyse the study's data. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the hypotheses. This analysis will be facilitated by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2: Questionnaire Distribution and Retrieval

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage
Number Distributed	310	100%
Number Retrieved and Used	281	90.7%

The Table 2 indicates 310 questionnaires were distributed, representing 100% of the total. Of these, 281 were successfully retrieved and used in the study, accounting for approximately 90.7% of the total distributed. This high response rate suggests strong participant engagement, but it's also important to consider potential reasons for the non-retrieval or non-use of some questionnaires, such as lack of time, interest, or understanding among participants. Understanding these factors can help improve response rates in future studies.

Table 3: Demographic Characteristics

Items	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Gender				
Male	123	43.8	43.8	43.8
Female	158	56.2	56.2	100.0
Total	281	100.0	100.0	100.0
Age Group				
Below 25 years	72	25.6	25.6	25.6
25 – 34 years	110	39.1	39.1	64.7
35 – 44 years	47	16.7	16.7	81.4
45 – 54 years	32	11.4	11.4	92.8
55 years and above	20	7.2	7.2	100.0
Total	281	100.0	100.0	100.0
Marital Status				
Single	116	41.3	41.3	41.3
Married	139	49.4	49.4	90.7
Others	26	9.3	9.3	100.0
Total	281	100.0	100.0	100.0
Educational qualification				
OND/Diploma	32	11.4	11.4	11.4
B.Sc/HND	140	49.8	49.8	61.2
MS.c/MBA	61	21.7	21.7	82.9
PhD	22	7.8	7.8	90.7
Others	26	9.3	9.3	100
Total	281	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 3 provides information on the study's demographic distribution. The demographic characteristics of the respondents in the study exhibit a diverse representation, providing valuable insights into the composition of the sample. Gender distribution shows a slight predominance of female respondents, comprising 56.2% of the sample, while males constitute 43.8%. Regarding age groups, the largest proportion falls within the 25 to 34 years category (39.1%), followed by those below 25 years (25.6%). Marital status reveals that married respondents form the majority (49.4%), followed closely by single individuals (41.3%), with a smaller proportion categorized under "Others" (9.3%). In terms of educational qualification, respondents predominantly hold B.Sc/HND degrees (49.8%), followed by MS.c/MBA qualifications (21.7%) and OND/Diploma certificates (11.4%). A smaller percentage of respondents possess PhD degrees (7.8%), while the "Others" category encompasses 9.3% of the sample. Overall, the diverse demographic profile of the respondents enhances the representativeness of the study and enriches the understanding of work-life balance and organizational commitment dynamics within the Nigerian banking industry.

Univariate Analyses

Table 4 Descriptive Statistics on Items Work-Life Balance and Organizational Commitment

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation	Decision Rule
WORK-LIFE BALANCE			
Role Engagement:			
I feel equally engaged and satisfied in my work and non-work domains.	4.32	.6037	Accept
I manage to keep the strains from work from affecting my personal life.	4.39	.6553	Accept
I have established clear boundaries between my work and personal life.	4.16	.7182	Accept
Role Conflict:			
I have enough time to fulfil both my work and personal responsibilities.	4.15	.7020	Accept
I am able to leave work-related stress at the office and fully engage in personal activities.	4.09	.7350	Accept
I often have to switch between behaviours when at work from when outside work conditions.	3.60	.8279	Accept
ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT			
Affective Commitment:			
I feel a strong emotional attachment to my organization.	4.68	.6521	Accept
I feel a sense of belonging and loyalty towards my organization.	4.71	.6491	Accept

I am invested in the goals and success of my organization.	4.65	.6545	Accept
Continuance Commitment:			
I continue to work in my organization because of the perceived costs associated with leaving.	4.47	.6751	Accept
I consider the potential drawbacks of leaving my current organization.	3.80	1.0061	Accept
I rely on my current organization for financial security and stability.	4.25	.7116	Accept
Normative Commitment:			
I feel a sense of obligation to remain with my current organization.	4.42	.7623	Accept
It is important for me to maintain a long-term relationship with my organization.	4.23	.7911	Accept
I feel that my organization has invested a lot in me, and I should reciprocate by staying.	4.17	.8308	Accept

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 4 offer insights into both work-life balance and organizational commitment within the study's sample. Regarding work-life balance, respondents generally exhibit high levels of agreement across Role Engagement and Role Conflict items, indicating a sense of satisfaction, clear boundaries between work and personal life, and minimal interference of work-related stress on personal activities. Similarly, organizational commitment is evident through strong agreement among respondents on Affective, Continuance, and Normative Commitment items, highlighting emotional attachment, loyalty, and a sense of obligation towards the organization. Overall, the findings suggest a positive organizational environment characterized by employees who feel engaged, satisfied, and committed to their work, with work-life balance initiatives likely playing a role in fostering this positive atmosphere.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 5: Role Engagement and Affective Commitment (Test for H₀₁)

		Role Engagement	Affective Commitment
Role Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.721**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Affective Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.721**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 5 presents the correlation analysis between Role Engagement and Affective Commitment, testing for the null hypothesis (H_{01}). The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role Engagement and Affective Commitment is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), with a strong positive correlation coefficient of .721. This result indicates a substantial positive relationship between Role Engagement and Affective Commitment among the study participants, suggesting that higher levels of Role Engagement are associated with higher levels of Affective Commitment, supporting the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_{01}).

Table 6: Employee Role Engagement and Continuance Commitment (Test for H_{02})

		Role Engagement	Continuance Commitment
Role Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Continuance Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.587**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 6 displays the correlation analysis between Employee Role Engagement and Continuance Commitment, examining the hypothesis H_{02} . The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role Engagement and Continuance Commitment is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), with a robust positive correlation coefficient of .587. This result indicates a substantial positive relationship between Role Engagement and Continuance Commitment among the study participants, suggesting that higher levels of Role Engagement correspond to higher levels of Continuance Commitment. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{02} is rejected, affirming the existence of a significant positive association between Employee Role Engagement and Continuance Commitment.

Table 7: Role Engagement and Normative Commitment (Test for H_{03})

		Role Engagement	Normative Commitment
Role Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Normative Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.623**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 7 illustrates the correlation analysis between Role Engagement and Normative Commitment, assessing the hypothesis H_{03} . The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role

Engagement and Normative Commitment is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), exhibiting a strong positive correlation coefficient of .623. This outcome suggests a substantial positive relationship between Role Engagement and Normative Commitment among the study participants. Hence, higher levels of Role Engagement are associated with higher levels of Normative Commitment. Consequently, the null hypothesis H_{03} is rejected, confirming the presence of a significant positive correlation between Role Engagement and Normative Commitment.

Table 8: Employee Role Conflict and Affective Commitment (Test for H_{04})

		Role Conflict	Affective Commitment
Role Engagement	Pearson Correlation	1	.576**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Affective Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.576**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 8 presents the correlation analysis between Employee Role Conflict and Affective Commitment, testing for the hypothesis H_{04} . The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role Conflict and Affective Commitment is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), with a strong positive correlation coefficient of .576. This result indicates a significant positive relationship between Employee Role Conflict and Affective Commitment among the study participants, suggesting that higher levels of Role Conflict correspond to higher levels of Affective Commitment. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{04} is rejected, affirming the existence of a significant positive association between Employee Role Conflict and Affective Commitment.

Table 9: Employee Role Conflict and Continuance Commitment (Test for H_{05})

		Role Conflict	Continuance Commitment
Role Conflict	Pearson Correlation	1	.619**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Continuance Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.619**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 9 displays the correlation analysis between Employee Role Conflict and Continuance Commitment, examining the hypothesis H_{05} . The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role Conflict and Continuance Commitment is statistically significant at the 0.01 level (two-

tailed), demonstrating a robust positive correlation coefficient of .619. This finding suggests a substantial positive relationship between Employee Role Conflict and Continuance Commitment among the respondents, indicating that higher levels of Role Conflict are associated with higher levels of Continuance Commitment. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{05} is rejected, confirming the presence of a significant positive correlation between Employee Role Conflict and Continuance Commitment.

Table 1: Role Conflict and Normative Commitment (Test for H_{06})

		Role Conflict	Normative Commitment
Role Conflict	Pearson Correlation	1	.603**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	281	281
Normative Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.603**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	281	281

Table 10 presents the results of the correlation analysis between Role Conflict and Normative Commitment, evaluating hypothesis H_{06} . The Pearson correlation coefficient between Role Conflict and Normative Commitment is highly significant at the 0.01 level (two-tailed), with a coefficient of .603. This finding indicates a strong positive relationship between Role Conflict and Normative Commitment among the participants, suggesting that higher levels of Role Conflict are associated with increased levels of Normative Commitment. Therefore, the null hypothesis H_{06} is rejected, confirming the existence of a significant positive correlation between Role Conflict and Normative Commitment.

Discussion of Findings

The primary aim of this study was to examine the relationship between work-life balance and organizational commitment among employees in a Nigerian context. The predictor variable, work-life balance, was measured through dimensions such as role engagement and role conflict, while organizational commitment served as the criterion variable, encompassing affective, continuance, and normative commitment. The discussion of the findings is presented below in accordance with the hypothesized relationships.

The results of the correlation analysis indicate a significant positive relationship between role engagement and affective commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .721, suggesting that approximately 72% of the variance in affective commitment can be explained by role engagement. This finding underscores the importance of fostering a work

environment where employees feel equally engaged and satisfied in their work and non-work domains, as it contributes significantly to their emotional attachment, sense of belonging, and investment in the organization. These results align with previous research by Malone and Issa (2013), emphasizing the role of employee engagement in enhancing organizational commitment.

Furthermore, the correlation analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between role engagement and continuance commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .587, indicating that approximately 59% of the variance in continuance commitment can be attributed to role engagement. This underscores the importance of maintaining clear boundaries between work and personal life and providing employees with sufficient time to fulfil their responsibilities in both domains. Employees who are able to manage work-related stress and maintain a healthy work-life balance are more likely to remain in the organization due to perceived costs associated with leaving, thus contributing to continuance commitment. These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Oyewobiet *al* (2022), highlighting the impact of work-life balance on employee retention.

Moreover, the correlation analysis demonstrates a significant positive relationship between role engagement and normative commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .623, indicating that approximately 62% of the variance in normative commitment can be explained by role engagement. This suggests that employees who perceive their organization as supportive of their work-life balance are more likely to feel a sense of obligation and loyalty towards the organization, leading to higher levels of normative commitment. These findings are in line with prior research by Caleb *et al.* (2020), emphasizing the role of organizational support in fostering normative commitment among employees.

The correlation analysis indicates a significant positive relationship between role conflict and affective commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .576. This suggests that approximately 58% of the variance in affective commitment can be explained by role conflict. The findings imply that employees who experience role conflict, such as struggling to balance work and personal responsibilities or experiencing stress from work that spills over into their personal lives, are more likely to exhibit lower levels of emotional attachment and loyalty towards the organization. This aligns with prior research suggesting that conflicts between work and personal life can negatively impact affective commitment (Mordiet *al.*, 2013). Therefore, organizations should strive to minimize role conflicts by implementing

policies and practices that support employees in managing their work-life balance effectively, thereby fostering stronger emotional bonds with the organization.

The correlation analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between role conflict and continuance commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .619. This indicates that approximately 62% of the variance in continuance commitment can be attributed to role conflict. The results suggest that employees who experience role conflict, such as feeling pressured to remain in their current job due to financial concerns or perceiving high costs associated with leaving the organization, are more likely to exhibit higher levels of continuance commitment. This finding is consistent with previous research highlighting the role of perceived costs and obligations in influencing continuance commitment (Scrima, *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, organizations should be mindful of the potential impact of role conflict on employees' continuance commitment and work towards minimizing such conflicts through supportive work-life balance initiatives and policies.

The correlation analysis demonstrates a significant positive relationship between role conflict and normative commitment, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of .603. This suggests that approximately 60% of the variance in normative commitment can be explained by role conflict. The findings indicate that employees who experience role conflict, such as feeling obligated to stay with the organization despite personal preferences or external pressures, are more likely to exhibit higher levels of normative commitment. This aligns with prior research suggesting that perceived obligations and investments in the organization can influence normative commitment (Caleb *et al.*, 2020). Therefore, organizations should be cognizant of the potential impact of role conflict on employees' normative commitment and strive to create a supportive work environment that values employee well-being and fosters a sense of loyalty and obligation towards the organization.

Overall, the findings of this study underscore the importance of promoting work-life balance initiatives in organizations as they positively influence various dimensions of organizational commitment, including affective, continuance, and normative commitment. Organizations that prioritize employee well-being and support work-life balance are likely to experience higher levels of employee engagement, retention, and commitment, ultimately contributing to organizational success and competitiveness.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the study highlights the interconnectedness between work-life balance and organizational commitment and emphasizes the need for organizations to implement strategies that promote work-life balance and enhance employee commitment. The analysis revealed significant correlations between various dimensions of work-life balance, such as role engagement and role conflict, and different types of organizational commitment, including affective, continuance, and normative commitment. These findings underscore the importance of addressing work-life balance issues in the workplace to promote stronger organizational commitment among employees. Based on the results, it is evident that factors influencing work-life balance, such as the ability to manage work and personal responsibilities effectively and establish clear boundaries between work and personal life, play a crucial role in shaping employees' commitment to the organization. By fostering a supportive work environment that values employee well-being and provides resources and support for managing work-life balance, organizations can cultivate a more engaged and committed workforce.

Recommendations for organizations include:

1. Organizations can implement flexible work arrangements, such as telecommuting and flexible hours, to accommodate employees' diverse needs and preferences.
2. Organizations can take the initiative to provide resources and support for managing work-related stress and promoting mental health and well-being initiatives.
3. Organizations can also offer or encourage employees to attend training and development programmes to help employees enhance their time management and work-life balance skills.

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